

INFLUENCE OF INDIVIDUAL-LEVEL ENTREPRENEURIAL ORIENTATION TOWARDS DIGITAL COMPETENCE: MODERATING IMPACT OF TECHNICAL COMPETENCE OF MIDDLE MANAGERS

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PURPOSE AND BACKGROUND

Successful Digital Transformation (DT) essentially needs to address workforce transformation where organizations are expected to address fundamental elements of their employees (Eden et al., 2018). Resistance to transformation program, which may trigger within the company and from its own employees, if not addressed carefully (Gresov et al., 1993). Further lack of cognitive awareness may prevent large and incumbent organizations from fully engaging with its digitalization program given existing and legacy practices, organizational structures, architectures, procedures were deep rooted during pre-digital phase (Hanelt et al., 2021). As a result, many organizations are trying to reposition themselves with an organization-wide DT program involving a well-structured digital strategy, business model, organization structure and next generation IT infrastructure (Verhoef et al., 2021). However less than 30% have been successful with DT initiatives while estimated 70% failures were found mainly due to complex organizational change efforts where people are involved (McKinsey, 2018; Neves et al., 2018). Recent research revealed that leadership and employees are the key for the overall success of DT (Canterino et al., 2020; Weber et al., 2022). Innovative and disruptive changes associated with DT program make leadership and employees a demanding and complex task to accomplish (Cortellazzo et al., 2019). While adapting to a dynamic market environment, leaders and employees of organizations are expected to play different and competing roles to deal with behavioral complexity inherited in DT program (Lawrence et al., 2009). Even though digital technologies play a major role in its transformation program, the success or failure will heavily

depend on employees' competencies, skills, attitude, and mindset (Gilbert, 2006; Tripsas M & Gavetti G, 2000; Zimmer M P, 2020).

Dynamic and competitive market environments will demand leaders and employees to develop and implement a well thought out, debated and structured digital strategy to enhance the organization performance (Matt et al., 2016). Leaders must simultaneously deal with employees who closely engage and work with digital technologies to understand its use cases for internal efficiency improvements and external market development (Cascio & Montealegre, 2016). Leaders should also identify and understand their subordinates who are employees responsible for the execution of many of these activities and their strengths and weaknesses to have a plan to get their maximum contribution for the successful implementation (McClanahan, 2020). There is evidence from existing research on both senior and middle managers and their need to have a strategic influence towards the business transformation, particularly in the digital era where organizations are actively engaging with many digital initiatives (Alexiev et al., 2010; Balogun & Johnson, 2005). Competent employees and managers can use their knowledge and experience in their organizational context and their colleagues, subordinates, and superiors to influence those around them to adopt organizational changes (Buchanan, 2008; Fairhurst, 2008; Pye & Pettigrew, 2005; Rouleau & Balogun, 2011).

INDIVIDUAL-LEVEL ENTREPRENEURIAL ORIENTATION

Entrepreneurial Orientation was initially studied related to top managers and owners of organizations, who will set and define actions related to strategic posture in achieving their entrepreneurial endeavors (Covin et al., 2020; Covin & Slevin, 1989; Lumpkin & Dess, 1996; Miller, 1983). This concept was later extended to the organization level, remained at the strategic level where top managers drive towards proactive, risk taking and innovative perspectives across the organization (Covin & Slevin, 1991). Recent researchers extended the entrepreneurial orientation to all employees across the organization, particularly to deal with uncertainty, complexity, and diversity associated with technology and innovations inherited in digitally disrupting markets (Bolton & Lane, 2012; Kraus et al., 2019; Mustafa et al., 2018). Eventually it has become a collective responsibility of all employees including top managers and middle managers for generating the entrepreneurship in their organizations and practice and promote proactive, risk taking and innovative behavior (Kraus et al., 2019)

DIGITAL COMPETENCE

Digital is a systematic evolution of IT/ICT and strategic information systems with its close integration with business and operational objectives, which are beyond traditional IT infrastructure related services. Digital competence was largely researched and examined between teacher – student context. However, there is very

little research at organization and employee level who are driving the organization through the DT journey.

Therefore, it is important that we closely examine the competence of IT professionals, IT competence of business managers, digital competence of educators and finally digital competence of employees. This approach will also help to understand and explore the specific aspects of competence of IT professionals, which was later evolved to digital competence. Digital work requires organizing human experiences with the support of human brain and digital media such that it will create new products and services and value to their business processes (Fuchs & Sevigani, 2013). A study (Murawski & Bick, 2017) highlights major challenges of a company is for their employees to adapt their culture, mindset, and competencies to the digital way of working rather than dealing with technology, innovations, and customer behavior.

Rapid technology adaption and its domestication depends on the core transformation competence such as literacy, which in turn is changing in its meaning as new technologies, business models and new practices evolve (Leu, 2000; Silverstone & Hirsch, 1994). The way we read, write, listen, and communicate are significantly different than few decades ago and therefore it is the time for our employees to think of digital competence as a basic need to function in our organizations and even as a survival skill to develop (Bawden, 2008; Eshet-alkalai, 2004; Martin & Grudziecki, 2006). Based on the conceptual framework developed (Eshet-alkalai, 2004), employees who work in digital environment need multiple complimentary skills, which involve more than ability to deal with digital applications rather includes large variety of cognitive, motor, sociological and emotional skills. Digital competence is required to be understood in its wider sense, where 15 different frameworks were analyzed to highlight key aspects, which can be summarized as follows (Ferrari et al., 2012).

- a. **Information management** – Identify, locate, access, retrieve, store, and organize information.
- b. **Collaboration** – Connect with others, participate in online network and communities, interact constructively.
- c. **Communication and sharing** - Communicate through online systems, considering privacy, safety, and correct online behaviour.
- d. **Creation of Content and Knowledge** - Integrate and re-elaborate previous content and knowledge, construct new knowledge
- e. **Ethics and Responsibility** - Behave in an ethical and responsible way, aware of legal frameworks
- f. **Evaluation and Problem-solving** - Identify digital needs, solve problems through digital means, assess the information retrieved
- g. **Technical Operations** - Use technology and media to perform tasks through digital tools

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Digital technologies also paved the way for new ventures, collaborations and partnerships leveraging existing resources, including open and shared technologies (Shen et al., 2018). This changed the mentality of employees who were expected to develop new skills and competencies related to digital technologies, business models and entrepreneurship (Domenico et al., 2014). Given the uncertainty created by the emergence of digital technologies on its desired outcomes given complex and dynamic market conditions and consumer behavior, it is interesting to investigate the influence of individual level entrepreneurial orientation towards digital competencies of employees. Many researchers highlighted the aspects related to digital entrepreneurship. On the other hand, employees are expected to be multidisciplinary (Yanez et al., 2010) and develop their entrepreneurship to deal with inherent characteristics such as complexity, diversity, information asymmetry and uncertainty (Garud & Karnøe, 2003; Ries, 2011). However, there is little focus in research to understand the relationship between individual level entrepreneurial orientation and digital competence of employees.

Literature related to employees highlighted the importance of middle managers, who are the supervising officers of employees in guiding and coaching in their journey towards a digitally matured organization (Carol A & Gloria L L, 1992; Larsen, 1993; Minh et al., 2017a). Further in digitally matured organizations, middle managers and employees appreciate the great deal teamwork (Aronson et al., 2006) unlike subordinate superior relationship in legacy organizations. They freely share ideas, information through open discussions and debate to understand the best technology propositions to come up with best business case for their organization (Chantias et al., 2019). In this process, the role of middle managers will have an impact to the relationship between the entrepreneurial orientation and digital competence of employees with their significant role, particularly with their technical competence acquired over a period with a lot of knowledge and experience. However, there is little research to understand the effect of middle managers' technical competence in the relationship of entrepreneurial orientation and digital competence of employees.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of this research study can be summarized as follows.

- 1) To investigate the relationship between Individual-level Entrepreneurial Orientation (IEO) consisting of following three aspects with Digital Competence of employees
 - a. Individual-level Proactiveness Orientation (IPO)
 - b. Individual-level Risk Taking Orientation (IRO)
 - c. Individual-level Innovativeness Orientation (IIO)

- 2) To investigate the moderating effect of Technical Competence of middle managers to the relationship between Individual-level Entrepreneurial Orientation and Digital Competence of employees.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This proposed study will find the answers to the following two research questions empirically.

- 1) How does Individual-level Entrepreneurial Orientation (IEO) consisting of following three aspects will affect Digital Competence of employees?
 - a. Individual-level Proactiveness Orientation (IPO)
 - b. Individual-level Risk Taking Orientation (IRO)
 - c. Individual-level Innovativeness Orientation (IIO)
- 2) What is the moderating effect of Technical Competence (middle managers) to the above relationship between Individual-level Entrepreneurial Orientation and Digital Competence of employees?

STUDY DESIGN

Based on the literature review, research objectives, research questions and theoretical insight, the following research model of employees' digital competence is presented in Figure 1. This conceptual model visually summarizes the relationship between employees' entrepreneurial orientation and employees' digital competence and the moderating influence of middle managers' technical competence.

Figure 1. Conceptual model of employees' digital competence at Sri Lanka Telecom

The following six numbers of hypotheses have been derived from the literature review, theoretical insight, and research objectives to investigate the relationships between variables.

Hypothesis 1: Individual level proactiveness of employees will be positively related to digital competence of employees.

Hypothesis 2: Individual level risk taking of employees will be positively related to digital competence of employees.

Hypothesis 3: Individual level innovativeness of employees will be positively related to digital competence of employees.

Hypothesis 4: Technical competence of middle managers will positively moderate the relationship between individual level proactiveness of employees and digital competence of employees.

Hypothesis 5: Technical competence of middle managers will positively moderate the relationship between individual level risk taking of employees and digital competence of employees.

Hypothesis 6: Technical competence of middle managers will positively moderate the relationship between individual level innovativeness of employees and digital competence of employees.

METHODOLOGY

This study will use a questionnaire survey to explore the hypothesized relationships of the proposed conceptual model. A structured questionnaire will be developed, and a survey will be carried out to conduct the research and collect data through responses to the questionnaires. The research process diagram including key steps are described in the Figure 2.

Figure 2. Research Process Diagram

SAMPLING AND DATA COLLECTION

Sri Lanka Telecom PLC, which is being the national ICT solution provider, is selected for the questionnaire survey given its size (7500 employees), capacity (national identity with global and local resources across the country), reach covering all geographical and ethnic groups. This study will collect data from approximately 400 engineers who involve in DT related activities in different departments and across the country to conduct the research. Engineers will answer questions related to their entrepreneurial orientation and three aspects, IPO, IRO, and IIO based on their judgement. The data collection the questionnaire survey is extended to middle managers, who are the direct supervising officers of Engineers, and leaders of DT related activities in their respective regions and departments. Middle Managers (130) will answer questions related to their technical competence and digital competence of their subordinates (400), who are engineers of this study. The E-mails, google forms and SurveyMonkey will be used as tools to

collect data efficiently. Items in these questionnaires regarding variables are developed based on the previously published constructs and literature.

CONSTRUCTS AND OPERATIONALIZATION

Data will be collected, and quantitative analysis will be carried out to measure and operationalize the constructs as described in Figure 3.1. In this study there are five constructs (IPO, IRO and IIO as independent variables under Entrepreneurial Orientation of Individuals, who are the employees at Sri Lanka Telecom PLC for this study, Employees' Digital Competence as the dependent variable and Middle Mangers' Technical Competence as moderating variable), which will be used and analyzed by operationalization of these constructs. Definitions of these constructs are adapted from previous studies with appropriate modifications suitable for this research study and current context of digitalization. A seven-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 ("strongly agree") to 7 ("strongly disagree") will be used in the questionnaire. Likert scale will be used in several research studies in digital and IT transformation studies (Gangwar et al., 2015; Y.-M. Wang et al., 2010), which are like this study. Based on previous research, social and demographic factors such as Age, Gender, Education, Job Tenure may affect to digital competence like other variables similar domains such as innovative work behavior of employees (Atitumpong & Badir, 2018). Such variables will be treated as control variables during the data analysis.

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